

Zinc Chloride-Phosphorus Oxychloride: A New Reagent in Organic Chemistry

J. L. Bose and R. C. Shah

A mixture of anhydrous zinc chloride and phosphorous oxychloride in certain proportions has been found to be surprisingly effective in a number of condensations in which the individual reagents are either ineffective or only slightly effective. This new reagent has been successfully used to bring about a number of condensations under comparatively mild conditions, sometimes even at the room temperature, providing good yields of the required products.

The new reagent was first used by Shah and Mehta (this *Journal*, 1936, 12, 368) for a successful synthesis of 2,4-dihydroxybenzophenone from benzamide or benzanilide and resorcinol. The use of this new reagent was revived recently by Grover, Shah, and Shah (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1955, 62; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3982) who found that hydroxybenzophenones and hydroxyxanthenes could be obtained in good yields by reacting *o*-hydroxybenzoic acids or their methyl ethers with polyhydric phenols or their methyl ethers in presence of the new reagent. It was also found that individually, anhydrous zinc chloride or phosphorus oxychloride was ineffective or only slightly effective in these condensations under the same conditions.

The efficiency of the new reagent is unique in view of the fact that other well-known condensing agents, such as, anhydrous aluminium, ferric, and, stannic chlorides, and their mixtures with phosphorus oxychloride were found to be ineffective in this reaction.

This method thus constitutes a new and convenient synthesis of hydroxybenzophenones and hydroxyxanthenes. The earlier method for the synthesis of hydroxyxanthenes

by heating a mixture of phenols and *o*-hydroxybenzoic acids with acetic anhydride at a high temperature (200°) afforded often poor yields and sometimes led to side reactions owing to the comparatively drastic reaction conditions (Michael, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1883, 5, 81; Kostannecki *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1896, 3981, *et. seq.*; Lund *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2438). As compared to this, very mild reaction conditions, such as, keeping the reaction mixture at the room temperature or heating it at 60-75° for a short period, are employed in the new method which usually furnishes good yields of hydroxyxanthenes.

In this new method, hydroxyxanthenes are obtained directly when the acid component is a 2,6-dihydroxybenzoic acid, such as, γ -resorcylic acid or phloroglucinol carboxylic acid, or when the phenolic component is either phloroglucinol or orcinol. This instantaneous cyclisation of the intermediate 2,6-dihydroxybenzophenones in these cases may have a stereochemical significance. In other cases hydroxybenzophenones are obtained which can be further converted to the corresponding xanthenes by heating with water under pressure at 180-200° (Grover, Shah and Shah, *loc. cit.*; Shah and Shah, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1956, 15B, 630; Dalal and Shah, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1957, 140; Kane, Kulkarni, and Shah, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18B, 28).

Several hydroxybenzophenones, viz., 2,4,2'-trihydroxy-3'-methyl-, 2,4,2'-trihydroxy-4'-methyl-, 2,3,4,2'-tetrahydroxy-, 2,4,2',4'-tetrahydroxy-, 2,2'-dihydroxy-4,4'-dimethoxy-, 2,3,4,2'-tetrahydroxy-3'-methyl-, 2,3,4,2'-tetrahydroxy-4'-methyl-, 2,4,2',3',4'-pentahydroxy- and 2,3,4,2',3',4'-hexahydroxy-benzophenones were prepared conveniently by this method and cyclised to the corresponding hydroxyxanthenes. Similarly, a number of hydroxyxanthenes, viz., 1-hydroxy-3-methyl-, 1-hydroxy-3,5-dimethyl-, 1-hydroxy-3,6'-dimethyl-, 1,3-dihydroxy-, 3,8-dihydroxy-, 1,3-dihydroxy-5-methyl-, 1,3-dihydroxy-6-methyl-, 1,6-dihydroxy-3-methyl-, 1,8-dihydroxy-3-methyl-, 1-hydroxy-5-methoxy-3-methyl-, 1-hydroxy-7-methoxy-3-methyl-, 1,3,6-trihydroxy-, 1,3,8-trihydroxy-, 3,4,8-trihydroxy-, 1,5,6-trihydroxy-3-methyl-, 1,6,8-trihydroxy-3-methyl-, 1,3-dihydroxy-5-methoxy-, 1,3-dihydroxy-7-methoxy-, 1,3-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-, 1,3,5,6-tetrahydroxy-, 1,3,6,8-tetrahydroxy-, 1,3,8-trihydroxy-5-methoxy-, and 1,3,8-trihydroxy-7-methoxy-xanthenes were obtained by the new method from the appropriate acids and phenols.

It may be noted that 2,4,2',4'-tetrahydroxybenzophenone, which has recently been found to be a very effective ultraviolet absorber, appears to be produced commercially under the name, Uvinul D-50 by the method of Grover, Shah, and Shah (*loc. cit.*) with the modification that 85% phosphoric acid is used in addition to make the mixture easily stirrable. The yield obtained, however, is the same, viz. 75% (Kirk and Othmer, "Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology", Second Supplement, Interscience Encyclopedia Inc., New York, 1950, p894; Stanley, U.S. P. 2,854, 485/1958).

In view of the success of the new reagent in the synthesis of hydroxybenzophenones and hydroxyxanthenes, investigations were carried out for its possible use in other reactions. It was found that phenols, free or protected, could be made to react with aliphatic and arylacetic acids in presence of the new reagent under mild conditions, often at the room temperature, providing good yields of the corresponding aryl alkyl ketones and deoxybenzoin respectively (Bose and Shah, Indian Patents 57888/1956; 60826/1957).

This new and simple method of synthesis of aryl alkyl ketones and deoxybenzoin, in which the acids are used directly and fairly good yields are obtained, has its obvious advantages in many cases over the Friedel-Crafts, Fries, and the Hoesch reaction or methods

involving the use of more costly and hazardous condensing agents, such as, boron trifluoride or hydrofluoric acid. The following industrially important ketonic intermediates are best prepared by the method: hexylresorcinol (75-80% yield) required for the preparation of the well-known urinary antiseptic and veterinary anthelmintic hexylresorcinol, *p*-hydroxypropiofenone (80-84% yield) required for the preparation of the synthetic oestrogen dienestrol and deoxyanisoin (80% yield), the key-intermediate for the production of the synthetic oestrogen diethylstilbestrol. In addition to these a number of other aryl alkyl ketones and deoxybenzoins were prepared by this method from the appropriate phenols and acids. These are: *p*-hydroxy- and *p*-methoxy-acetophenones, 4-hydroxy-2-methylacetophenone, *p*-methoxypropiofenone, *p*-hexyl diphenyl ether, 4-acetyl- and 2-acetyl-1-naphthols, resacetophenone, stearylresorcinol, γ -orcacetophenone, ω -chloroacetyl-catechol, 4-hydroxy-, 4-methoxy-, 4-phenoxy-, 4-hydroxy-2-methyl-, 4,4'-dihydroxy-, 4-hydroxy-4'-methoxy-, 2,4-dihydroxy-, 2,4-dihydroxy-4' methoxy-deoxybenzoins, and 4-phenylacetyl and 2-phenylacetyl-1-naphthols.

A specific advantage of this method of synthesis of aryl alkyl ketones and deoxybenzoins is the almost exclusive formation of the *p*-compound in most cases.

The most important application of this new reagent so far is for the production of 4-hydroxycoumarin and its derivatives in good yields by a direct condensation of phenols with malonic acids in presence of this reagent under mild reaction conditions (Shah, Bose, and Shah, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 677; Indian Patent 62890/1958, B.P. 858110/1959). Other agents like stannic chloride, aluminium chloride, or ferric chloride, either individually or their mixtures with phosphorus oxychloride, are almost ineffective in this reaction.

The reaction between phenol and malonic acid under mild conditions, such as heating at 65-75° with the new reagent for 10-15 hrs., has furnished a high yield (60-65%) of the industrially important compound, 4-hydroxycoumarin, which is the key-intermediate for the production of a number of leading anticoagulant drugs like dicoumarol, tromexan and warfarin sodium, and also for the synthesis of modern anticoagulant rodenticides, warfarin and fumarin. This new one-stage process for the preparation of 4-hydroxycoumarin is simpler and appears to be more economic than the known methods for its manufacture, which involve two or more stages and require either costly starting materials or relatively drastic reaction conditions necessitating the use of costly equipments or complicated processing.

The following 4-hydroxycoumarins were prepared by this method: 4-hydroxycoumarin, 6-methyl-, 7-methyl-, 8-methyl-, 5,8-dimethyl-, 5-methyl-, 8-isopropyl-, 1-thio-, 3-phenyl-, 6-phenyl-, 3-ethyl-, 3-propyl^{1a}-, 3-butyl^{1a}-, 3-hexyl^{1a}-, 3-4, octyl^{1a}-, 4-hydroxycoumarins, 4-hydroxy-5,6- and 7,8-benzo-coumarins, 4, 7-dihydroxycoumarin, 4,4'-dihydroxy-6,6'-dicoumarin.

This reaction between a phenol and a malonic acid to afford 4-hydroxycoumarins

probably proceeds *via* monophenyl malonate formed as an intermediate. This was supported by the fact that monophenyl malonate gave 4-hydroxycoumarin in the presence of the new reagent.

Small amounts of diphenyl malonate were found to be formed as a byproduct in the new method for the preparation of 4-hydroxycoumarin. That diphenyl malonate was not an intermediate in the new synthesis was shown by the fact that pure diphenyl malonate alone or a mixture of phenol and malonic acid in the molar proportion of 2:1 failed to produce any appreciable quantity of 4-hydroxycoumarin in presence of the new reagent. In the latter case diphenyl malonate was obtained as the main reaction product. It was found, however, that 4-hydroxycoumarins could be obtained in good yields if diaryl malonates were heated with one mole of the corresponding malonic acid in presence of the new reagent. This reaction constituted another new synthesis of 4-hydroxycoumarins (Shah, Bose, and Shah, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 623; Indian Patent 63083/1958).

The following 4-hydroxycoumarins were prepared by this method: 4-hydroxycoumarin, 6-methyl-, 7-methyl-, 8-methyl-, 5-methyl-3-isopropyl-, 1-thio-, 3-octylⁿ-4-hydroxycoumarins, and 4-hydroxy-7,8-benzo- and 4-hydroxy-5,6-(or 6,7)-benzocoumarins.

Analogous to the one-stage synthesis of 4-hydroxycoumarins from phenols and malonic acids is the new general synthesis of 2,4-dihydroxyquinoline, which has been achieved by reacting an aromatic primary amine with malonic acid in presence of the new reagent. This simple method appears to be very convenient for the synthesis of a number of 2,4-dihydroxyquinolines, which were previously prepared by long and cumbersome methods (Shah, Bose and Shah, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1960, 19B, 176; Indian Patent 65777/1958.)

The following 2,4 dihydroxyquinolines were prepared by this method: 2,4-dihydroxyquinoline, 6-chloro-, 7-chloro-, 5,8-dichloro-, 6-methyl-, 7-methyl-, 8-methyl-, 6-methoxy-, 8-methoxy-, and 3-octyl- 2,4-dihydroxyquinolines, 2,4-dihydroxy-7,8-benzo-, 2,4-dihydroxy-5,6 (or 6,7)-benzoquinolines, and 1,2-(2,4-dihydroxy-7, 8-pyridyl)-anthraquinone.

Aniline and malonic acid in presence of the new reagent furnished fairly good yield of 2,4-dihydroxyquinoline. It was also found that the same reaction could be brought about by phosphorus oxychloride alone, but the product was more difficult to purify. This latter procedure has been recently reported also by Ziegler and Gelfert (*Mh. Chem.*, 1959, 90, 822).